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California State University, Los Angeles
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DIRECT CLINICIAN CONTACT TO IMPROVE CERVICAL CANCER SCREENING
PARTICIPATION IN VETERANS

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Cervical cancer is caused by high risk types of human papilloma virus (hrHPV), persistent hrHPV infections may result in precancerous cervical lesions. Undetected lesions may slowly progress to invasive cervical cancer. Routine cervical cancer screenings (CCS) via papanicolau testing is recommended every 3 years for women aged 21-65, with an increased interval to every 5 years with hrHPV cotesting. Active duty service members experience a) increased rates of HPV infections and cervical dysplasias, b) increased incidence of cervical cancer, and c) decreased CCS rates. The purpose of this doctoral project was to increase CCS participation rates in veteran patients aged 21-65 by providing 1:1 patient education on cervical cancer and the utilization of an evidence-based tool to collect patient perceived barriers to completing CCS. This quality improvement project was conducted at a level 1a Veterans Health Administration facility in southern California; the goals were to increase CCS rates by at least 10% from a baseline of 65.91% by 2023 calendar year end and to also determine primary patient perception barriers to CCS for dissemination to the women's health leadership team. A total of 1,159 women were eligible for CCS; 453 patients ranging from the ages of 21 to 65 years were categorized as overdue based on clinical reminder status. Of those, 39 contacts were attempted and 37 were provided CCS education. Of the 37 successful contacts, 6 patients completed their overdue screening within the implementation window. The CCS completion rate increased from 65.91% to 74.9% post intervention. 12 of the 37 veterans also consented to participate in a modified CPC-28 questionnaire to gather patient-reported barriers to timely CCS completion. Reported barriers included an absence of trust in the organization and patient lack of knowledge surrounding CCS guidelines. Results of the voluntary survey were shared with facility providers and leadership as potential seed for future care delivery improvement endeavors.

Keywords: cervical cancer screening, high risk human papilloma virus, women, veterans, patient perceived barriers

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Background

Cervical cancer is responsible for approximately 280,000 deaths annually in developed countries, an estimated 4,300 women in the United States will die from the disease in 2020 (Popalis et al., 2022). The World Health Organization recognizes the disease as preventable through screening programs, early discovery improves the survival rate from 66% 91.8% for localized cancers (Kurt & Akyuz, 2019; Popalis et al., 2022). The causative agent for cervical cancer is high risk type human papilloma virus (hrHPV); most infections will spontaneously resolve without incident, however, persistent hrHPV infections can result in precancerous cervical lesions (Sawaya et al., 2019). Lingering, undetected hrHPV related lesions may slowly progress to non-localized, invasive cervical cancer, in fact, 30% of cervical intraepithelial neoplasia grade 3 lesions take 30 years to progress to a cancerous state (Sawaya et al., 2019). Screening programs inclusive of Papanicolaou (pap) smear and hrHPV testing provide reliable means for early detection. The American Academy of Family Physicians, United States Preventative Services Task Force (USPSTF), American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists (ACOG), and the American Society for Colposcopy and Cervical Pathology recommend screening via pap smears every three years for women between the ages of 21-65 years of age, with an increased interval to every five years for those aged 30-65 with hrHPV co-testing (McDermott et al., 2021).

Routine screening following national guidelines is critical in decreasing cervical cancer incidence. In the U.S., only 81% of women participate in Cervical Cancer Screening (CCS) per guidelines and 50%-70% of cervical cancer diagnoses belong to those who were not screened within the last five years (Suk et al., 2022). Active-duty service members (ADSM) experience a higher incidence of human papilloma virus (HPV) infection and HPV cervical dysplasias as

compared to the general population. There is limited evidence explaining the cause for increased rates of HPV and cervical dysplasias within the population (Seay et al., 2022). However, due to the increased incidence, ADSM are at a higher risk of cervical cancer; combined with inadequate screening in this population, the group faces quite a precarious situation (Seay et al., 2022). ADSM transition to veteran status does not negate the outcome of low screening rates and increased risk incurred while actively serving.

Potential barriers to completing CCS include a history of sexual assault, outcome distress, and health service obstacles (Arrivillaga et al., 2023; Danan et al., 2022). As of 2018, women represent approximately 10% of U.S. veterans, it is anticipated women will comprise 16.3% by year 2043. In women veterans, history of sexual assault was not found to be a significant barrier to screening completion, however, obstacles to the limited women's health services within the Veterans Health Administration (VHA) have been previously identified (Danan et al., 2022; Marshall et al., 2021). Interventions at the system, provider, and patient level including introduction of women's health navigators, mailed screening reminders, and community outreach programs are considered effective interventions to increase CCS rates (Popalis et al., 2022).

Problem Statement

CCS programs inclusive of regular, timely, and appropriate Pap testing have been shown to reduce incidence by 34%-80% (Kurt & Akyuz, 2019). Nationally, 81% of women aged 21-65 completed screening per USPSTF guidelines; the Healthy People 2030 goal for CCS is 79.2% (Popalis et al., 2022; McDermott et al., 2021; Suk et al., 2022). At a level 1a VHA medical facility in Southern California in March 2023, the CCS rate described as the ePerformance metric (ePM) *ccs01_ec: Cervical Ca Screen*, was 65.91%. Internal obstacles were identified through chart review and interviews with women's health medical support assistants, licensed

vocational nurses, registered nurses, and physicians. There is evidence of screening documentation in the health record outside of clinical reminders, last-minute appointment cancellations by patients, provider preference for different screening algorithms, scheduling errors related to appointment duration to complete the test, patient preferences for few female providers, primary care providers referring patients to the gynecology department for screenings resulting in delays, primary care providers unaware of due screenings related to incorrect clinical reminders, military sexual trauma sequelae, and continuity of care gaps regarding medical record reconciliation of tests performed in other community healthcare systems. Evidence-based interventions described in the literature are multi-modal approaches inclusive of patient, provider, and system level changes.

In March 2023, 847 clinical reminders for women veteran medical records showed as due or overdue for Pap testing. Previous interventions to increase testing included credentialing efforts for primary care physicians to provide Pap testing and pelvic exams in addition to women's health physicians. The women's health department participates in 'Papacon' to accommodate psychosocial barriers to testing including childcare and employment challenges during the work week by holding Saturday screenings. While childcare issues have been cited in the literature as a potential barrier for women veterans in obtaining screenings, it is unclear if this particular factor is a true barrier for this facility's patients (Marshall et al., 2021). System and provider related changes have been implemented, however, from interviews with stakeholders and process owners there lacks evidence of an organized effort to obtain the voice of the customer. Successful, patient focused interventions in literature include clinician delivered patient education on CCS importance, Pap procedure, and proper screening intervals (Kurt & Akyuz, 2019; McDermott et al., 2021; Popalis et al., 2022).

Purpose Statement

Therefore, the purpose of this project was to increase CCS rates in veteran patients aged 21-65 by providing 1:1 patient education on CCS and utilize an evidence-based tool to collect patient perceived barriers to completing CCS.

Supporting Framework

Theoretical frameworks provide scaffolds to organize observed phenomena for critical thought; relationships between relevant concepts of the DNP project and those reaching broadly into other areas of knowledge are analyzed (University of Southern California [USC], 2023). While highlighting the connectedness of the project topic to other bodies of knowledge, frameworks also provide boundaries by focusing the user on specific variables of interest (USC, 2023). Models serve as a guide to support the Doctor of Nursing Practice candidates' project by providing a base for analysis and discussion, requiring the student to define the scope of the problem, state the aims of interventions, and determine data required to reach those stated aims, as a few examples (Bergstrom et al., 2020).

Logic Model

One such theoretical framework is the Logic Model (Appendix A), which is used for program implementation, design and planning, evaluation, and reporting, or as a roadmap for change (W. K. Kellogg Foundation, 2004). The model is comprised of both a) the theory of change, and b) the program logic model (Knowlton & Phillips, 2013). Logic models are utilized by such organizations as the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), United Nations, the World Bank, and the American Dental Association (W. K. Kellogg Foundation, 2004). The theory of change includes insights of an organization on how it believes a particular change or group of changes will unfold (Knowlton & Phillips, 2013). While the program logic model

provides details on the outcomes, resources, and planned interventions required for the change, the interconnectedness of each component allows for identification of fatalistic project design flaws at the outset, potentially avoiding issues with execution or sustainment (Idzik et al., 2021; Knowlton & Phillips, 2013). The model further supports sustainability by providing a replicable process capable of spread to others interested in reaching similar goals (Knowlton & Phillips, 2013). Plausible program models are necessary in order to have successful implementation and sustainment, theories of change are the foundation of program models and must also be based on evidence or at least a reasonable hypothesis (Knowlton & Phillips, 2013). The key elements of the logic model are divided between a) planned work for implementation and, b) desired results of the program (W. K. Kellogg Foundation, 2004). Resources and output fall under planned work, while short-term outcomes, intermediate-term outcomes, long-term outcomes, and impact are under intended results (Knowlton & Phillips, 2013).

Intended Results

As shown in Appendix A, each element is contained in its own column adjacent to the next. The final model is meant to be read left to right, while application moves from right to left starting with defining short, mid, and long-term project outcomes in SMART format: Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound (Idzik et al., 2021). Each component of the logic model is interrelated; determining anticipated resources and activities necessary to reach the intended outcome(s) deters arbitrary goal setting and encourages synchronicity between plan and action (Idzik et al., 2021). The long-term goal is the overall intended outcome measure for the program or project and also determines the impact of the project (Idzik et al., 2021). Early identification of goals allows for the development of indicators and benchmarks which will allow the project team to reliably assess progress (Idzik et al., 2021). Measures chosen for the outcome

phase may also be used as metrics during future program evaluations, as seen by the lowest row of the Figure 1 labeled evaluation (Knowlton & Phillips, 2013).

Planned Work

During the output phase, evidence-based practice is employed to determine effective interventions, or activities, to achieve determined goals (Idzik et al., 2021). The model's change theory is incorporated in the assumptions and external factors sections (Appendix A). The user is encouraged to provide context behind the situation in support of why the chosen interventions are expected to be successful (Sharp, 2021). The assumptions and additional context are included just above the evaluation row. Key stakeholders as well as other systems and processes the impending changes may impact are also identified during the output phase.

Inputs available to operate a program or implement and sustain a project are determined by the interventions from the previous phase and can include financial, human, or organizational resources (W. K. Kellogg Foundation, 2004). Inputs must be aligned with the type of program being developed and may also help determine useful indicators. Staffing or financial reports can be home to useful metrics for tracking (W. K. Kellogg Foundation, 2004). The model is helpful to visualize not only the implementation plan but also to consider issues such as potential budgetary effects the proposed change will have on an organization and proactively mitigate potential pitfalls (Idzik et al., 2021).

Framework Application

For this project, an adaptation of the logic model was utilized from the South Carolina Department of Education (Appendix A). The logic model is a tool to assess program progress or resolve a challenge. The model connects planned actions with their expected outcomes and clarifies complex or entangled components of a system or process (Knowlton & Phillips, 2013).

The project overall goal and challenge to overcome was to improve rates of CCS in veteran women. Preventative screenings are a complex process under the women's health program. As of 2019, 73.5% of U.S. women aged 21-65 completed their screenings as recommended by USPSTF, the women's health program in question is below this average by greater than 10% (National Cancer Institute, 2022). Alterations to the program's delivery of CCS will have an effect on other health system processes such as information technology's deployment of clinical reminders. Delivery is also complicated by variables such as preferred provider availability, military sexual trauma, appointment cancellations, and screening documentation outside of clinical reminders. For this project the logic model provided guidelines for narrowing the myriad of challenges by requiring priorities, setting both short- and long-term goals, determining stakeholders who were affected by the change, and focused on data to illustrate if the change was indeed improving intended outcomes. The tool supported conceptualization of the project, which was conducted under time constraints. The logic model incorporated goal setting which provided a clearer view of what could be accomplished within the time allotted (Idzik et al., 2021).

Review of Literature

A review of the literature was conducted to guide and support this quality improvement project, in conjunction with the logic framework described previously. The electronic databases employed for this project included CINAHL Plus, EBSCO, and PubMed. Search terms used across both databases included “cervical cancer screening and veterans,” “strategies to improve cervical cancer screening,” “Pap smear and primary care and cancer screening,” “military sexual trauma and cervical cancer,” “HPV and cervical cancer screening,” and “cervical cancer screening guidelines.”

The review yielded approximately 425 peer reviewed articles written in English and published between 2018 and 2023. Articles were further refined based on relevancy to project aims and excluded populations including women under the age of 21 years as CCS is not recommended by the USPSTF for this age group. Eleven articles were included in the final review.

Additional resources incorporated into this project include clinical practice guidelines for CCS including those of the USPSTF, ACOG, and the American Cancer Society (ACS). The project also incorporated internal policy and procedures from the Veteran Health Administration National Center for Health Promotion and Disease Prevention (NCP), and VHA Directive 1330.01(07) *Healthcare Services for Women Veterans*, dated September 9th, 2022.

CCS Clinical Guidelines

For women of average risk for cervical cancer, the ACS currently recommends CCS via primary hrHPV testing every five years beginning at age 25 years through 65 years as the primary testing tool (Auguste, 2021). Primary hrHPV DNA screening is a newer method of testing, which has been shown to be more effective at detecting precancerous and cancerous

lesions than Pap cytology testing in clinical trials, however, only two hrHPV tests, Cobas by Roche and BD's Onclarity, have been approved by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for the purpose of primary CCS (Aitken et al., 2019). FDA approved hrHPV primary testing platforms are not located nationwide (Aitken et al., 2019). If primary hrHPV testing is not available, the second tier is cytology co-test with HPV, and if that is not available, then a Pap test every three years is recommended (Auguste, 2021).

ACOG currently endorses the 2018 USPSTF screening guidelines (ACOG, 2021). The USPSTF screening guidelines have been dramatically changed since the 2012 rendition and start at an earlier age of 21 years, begin with cytology testing every three years, and then at age 30 incorporates either hrHPV testing alone every five years or in addition to Pap testing every 3 years until age 65 years (Sawaya et al., 2019). Patients without a cervix are exempted from both the ACS and USPSTF guidelines. (Auguste, 2021). USPSTF recommendations apply to individuals regardless of their sexual history, also, due to insufficient evidence to safely exclude vaccinated patients, adherence to both guidelines is independent of HPV vaccination status (Auguste, 2021).

The VHA NCP CCS guidelines and VHA directive 1330.01(06) both mirror the 2018 USPSTF screening guidelines and recommends cytology every three years for average risk women between the ages of 21-29, for women ages 30-65 the recommendation is cytology every three years, or hrHPV testing alone every five years, or hrHPV co-testing with cytology every five years. VHA also excludes patients who have had a total hysterectomy if they have no history of cervical cancer or high grade precancerous lesions, also, the test utilized for the hrHPV standalone option must be FDA approved.

CCS Barriers

Challenges to CCS participation includes patient lack of disease knowledge and recommended screening procedures, health beliefs including necessity of the screening given a lack of symptoms, fear of pain associated with the exam, fear of the test result, and psychosocial issues such as lack of childcare (Kurt & Akyuz, 2019; Arrivillaga et al., 2023). In discussions with VHA women's clinic staff, patient preference for limited female physicians was observed as a primary barrier to scheduling exams. Process barriers include opportunistic or patient dependent triggers for screening, uncoordinated efforts to ensure patients return for follow-up care, and lack of electronic health record (EHR) integration between health systems increasing difficulty in reliably determining if patients are due for screening (Feldman et al., 2017).

CCS Interventions to Improve Participation

Provider screening reminders integrated into EHR, and performance feedback have both been successful interventions for clinicians in increasing cancer screening rates (Feldman et al., 2017). Organizational change such as devoting resources to the development and sustainment of a clinic dedicated to preventative health was also found to effectively increase preventative screenings (Luckett, 2022). Effective screening programs utilize well-defined protocols and guidelines, regularly perform quality assurance via review of high-quality data, and incorporate continuous process improvement (Aitken et al., 2019). System changes including the expansion of role responsibilities has also been shown to increase preventative care participation; preventative health counseling provided by nonphysician staff has shown statistically significant increases in completion rates for Pap testing (Luckett, 2022).

Passive patient education interventions including brochures, mailings, audio recordings, and self-guided modules or videos reported statistically significant lower effect sizes than groups receiving care interventions inclusive of health care providers actively leading group education

sessions or serving as patient navigators (6.4% versus 16.2%) (Popalis et al., 2022). Interventions where healthcare workers conducted one on one patient education interactions experienced the highest, statistically significant effect rates on CCS at 16.1% versus 3.5%, and 55.9% versus 25.2%, compared to groups which received passive outreach such as mailed invitation/reminder to complete CCS (Popalis et al., 2022; Kurt & Akyuz, 2019). In another multimodal patient outreach study, outreach via email, provider written letter, or CDC informational flyer alone were not statistically significant compared to the control group in increasing CCS rates (Peitzmeier et al., 2016). The arm inclusive of provider phone calls to patients providing CCS education in addition to passive means of outreach (36%) and the intervention arm including only provider phone calls (29%) made statistically significant impact on CCS rates versus the control group which received opportunistic Pap testing during routine visits (21%) (Peitzmeier et al., 2016). Similar results were seen in a quasi-experimental study involving a primary care clinic caring for military families comparing direct physician phone call to patients explaining the need for screening and just in time scheduling of appointment versus opportunistic identification of screening need at annual physical, the study observed a statistically significant 45% CCS completion rate compared to the control at 13.9% (McDermott et al., 2021).

The literature review included 11 peer reviewed articles, two clinical practice guidelines, and two quality improvement articles. CCS guidelines contain varying screening intervals and testing methods which may increase variability of treatment protocols within an organization and prove confusing to some patients ultimately serving as a potential barrier. Health beliefs, understanding of treatment procedures, and outcome fear were also found to play a role in patient hesitancy to complete CCS (Arrivillaga et al., 2023; Kurt & Akyuz, 2019). CCS success has been observed in systems inclusive of protocols, quality assurance, provider reminders, and

continued process improvement (Aitken et al., 2019; Feldman et al., 2017). Interventions involving patient to clinician interaction including education on the necessity for CCS were found to be statistically significant, versus control methods such as opportunistic screenings at physical examination appointments, at increasing CCS rates.

Methods

This quality improvement DNP project took place at a level 1a VHA facility in southern California; the goals were to increase CCS rates by at least 10% from a baseline of 65.91% by 2023 calendar year end and to also determine primary patient perceived barriers to CCS for dissemination to the women's health leadership team within the facility. The clinician-led intervention assessed facility CCS rates two quarters prior to patient counseling and one quarter post. Within the facility, system and provider related changes have been implemented, however, from interviews with stakeholders and process owners there lacks evidence of an organized effort to obtain the voice of the customer. In addition to patient education, the clinician also incorporated use of an evidence-based tool to assess patient professed barriers to CCS completion. Results of the voluntary survey were shared with facility primary care providers, performance measures committee, and women's health leadership as potential seed for future care delivery improvement endeavors.

Ethical Considerations

The principal investigator for this project had no conflicts of interest to disclose. The project proposal was exempted by the Institutional review board (IRB) from both the VHA facility and California State University, Los Angeles. The facility women's health program manager and Pap nurse coordinator support the proposed project and a permission letter penned by the leadership team was secured prior to IRB submittal (Appendix F). Verbal consent was obtained from each patient contacted prior to initiating the intervention. Electronic patient information including survey responses were secured in a VHA supplied laptop which was only accessible by the Personal Identify Verification (PIV) card belonging to the primary investigator. Continuous credentialing and background checks were required under the Homeland Security

Presidential Directive 12, unique user access to federal information systems per card was granted and access was also protected by a rotating six-digit pin (U.S. Department of Commerce, n.d.). Prior to deidentification of patient data, the PIV protected computer remained on VHA property and in a locked office, within a locked cabinet when not actively being monitored by the primary investigator. Patient data was not stored on the computer's local memory, instead all data was saved to the VHA secured one drive file hosting service under the account specific only to the primary investigator's PIV access.

Sample

A contact list for the facility was obtained from the women's health CCS coordinator; a total of 1,159 women veterans were eligible for CCS. Simple, random sampling was utilized in this project, with every other overdue patient on the provided list being contacted. Of those 1,159 women, 453 patients ranging from the ages of 21 to 65 years were categorized as overdue based on clinical reminder status. Forty of the 453 overdue patients had no medical record documentation of historical CCSs. The project sampled patients from all departments where CCS occurs in the facility including women's health and primary care clinics. Patients not meeting USPSTF criteria for screening or currently under care for cervical cancer were excluded from the sample.

Setting

The level 1a VHA facility is located in southern California, care is provided for approximately 50,000 diverse veterans at the medical center, as well as 7 community-based satellite campuses throughout Orange and Los Angeles counties (Veterans Affairs, 2022). The women's health department provides comprehensive care for veterans in partnership with primary care providers. The program includes services such as gynecologic oncology, surgical

services, family planning, mental health supportive services, and preventative care including breast and CCSs (VA, 2022).

Measures

The CPC-28 scale, Creencias, Papanicolaou, Cancer-28, is validated and standardized with a Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.735$ (Svihrova et al., 2022) (Appendix C). The scale was developed in 2009 to examine women's beliefs about cervical cancer and Pap tests. The 28 statements across six domains reflects the scale's foundations in the Health Beliefs Model, which attributes behavior to individual beliefs (Svihrova et al., 2022; Urrutia & Hall, 2013). The scale begins with collecting patient demographic information, then transitions to capturing participant level of agreement with health belief statements via 4-point Likert scale, 1 = Strongly agree, 2 = Agree, 3 = Disagree, 4 - Strongly Disagree (Svihrova et al., 2022). The study used nine of the 28 statements, highlighted in Appendix C. The scale focused on patient barriers to completing CCS, the more agreeable the answer the stronger the barrier. Permission for use of the tool as modified was granted by the original author (Appendix D).

Intervention

CCS Education

Patients were contacted by telephone from October 14th, 2023, through November 14th, 2023. Calls were made via VHA associated phone numbers and the caller identity was not shielded. At the outset of each encounter an explanation of the project purpose, how the data would be utilized, subject participation was completely voluntary and that patients may refrain from answering any questions which make them uncomfortable were shared with the veteran. Patient verbal consent to participate in this improvement project was obtained prior to providing scripted patient education. Successful contacts resulted in clinician explaining the need for

screening following a modified script adapted from a randomized control trial exploring patient calls to improve CCS rates performed by Goldenberg (2010) (Appendix B). Patients were allowed to ask questions of the clinician pertaining to CCS. If a patient received education, this was collected in a de-identified spreadsheet.

Patient Survey

After education, patients were invited by the clinician to participate in the CPC-28 questionnaire. When verbal permission was granted by the veteran, the clinician administered the questionnaire over the phone.

CCS Appointment

Veterans were then offered a contact from the women's health department to assist in scheduling the screening. Interested patient information was shared with the CCS coordinator for follow-up. Patients who were unavailable at the time of the call but had voicemail set-up were provided with CCS educational script and a direct phone number to schedule a screening through voicemail. When voicemail was not available the contact was considered unsuccessful. Patients actively driving their vehicle or otherwise distracted were provided time to focus before initiating the intervention.

CCS Completions

Approximately eight-weeks after the intervention, patient records were reviewed to ascertain if Pap cytology had been completed either within the VA health system or in the community.

Evaluation

Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data. Survey data included narrative responses and Likert scale ratings, both were captured during the call and included in the data

analysis discussion (Appendix G). Provide more details on how you analyzed the data. Usually, the program used to run the statistics and specific procedures and tests used are included.

Results

Of the 453 patients identified as overdue at the time of intervention, 39 contacts were attempted, 37 patients were provided 1:1 CCS education. Of the 37 successful contacts, 12 veterans agreed to participate in the modified CPC-28 questionnaire to gather patient perceived barriers to completing CCS. Four of the 12 screens were positive. Patient identified obstacles in descending order of occurrence were, a) feelings of being treated poorly within the healthcare facility, and b) lack of CCS guideline knowledge, specifically recommended age range and screening intervals. Six patients completed CCS post intervention, two of which were conducted in the community, and there were zero results requiring follow-up. Baseline CCS eQM for the project was 65.91% with a goal to increase by at least 10%; at the end of the intervention window eQM had increased to 74.91%.

Discussion

CCS Education

The incidence of cervical cancer and resultant mortality rates associated with untimely detection remains a global public health priority (Arrivillaga et al., 2023). Screenings comprised of Pap cytology and hrHPV co-testing has reduced the U.S. incidence by over 50% in the past 30 years; barriers to screening such as PTSD exist for women veterans (Danan et al., 2022). Womens' experiences with screening can include fear of the tests' outcome, embarrassment, pain, and health services barriers (Arriveillaga et al., 2023). A systematic review including women with varying levels of access to care showed an 8% increase in screening adherence with 1:1 patient education, and telephone delivered patient reminders (37% uptake/ \$67) were more effective and less costly than both text (24% uptake/ \$100) or mailed letters (19% uptake/ \$133) (Firmino-Machado et al., 2018). One aspect of this quality improvement project was providing 1:1 patient education via telephone call to women veterans who were overdue for CCS. During the call, the principal investigator described the causative agent of cervical cancer, transmission of hrHPV, the slow evolution of precancerous cells, what to expect during the procedure, guideline-based ages for CCS, and the importance of completing timely screenings. Patients were encouraged to ask questions and express any thoughts or concerns they may have held with CCS. None of the patients expressed distrust in CCS or USPSTF recommended intervals, few patients shared this was the first educational opportunity they experienced with CCS from a VA clinician. Younger patients queried of required preparation needed for the screening. Most patients expressed they would be agreeable to completing their overdue screening. A teach back method was not utilized due to the existing patient time requirement for each session, however, this may have supported reinforcement of topics discussed during the 1:1.

Survey for CCS Barriers

In terms of CCS barriers in behavioral health patients, some healthcare providers believe, a) the stigma of mental health conditions preclude some patients from seeking routine screening, b) untreated behavioral health conditions consume most of the time available during an encounter, and c) trauma sequelae may present as barriers in patient communication and decreased trust in providers (Mkuu et al., 2022).

Twelve patients who received education also consented for the modified CPC-28 barrier survey, four of these responses were positive for at least one CCS barrier (Appendix G). Two central themes emerged from responses: a lack of trust in the health care organization, a gap in patient knowledge of recommended screening intervals. Concerns with trust were described as perceived untimely provider responses, perceived inadequate care for acute and chronic conditions, staff behavior described as unfriendly, and perceived unwarranted denials for specific treatments. Some of the incidents described as trust concerns occurred in departments outside of women's health yet still affected CCS completions; patient narratives described a distrust of the facility, independent of where it occurred. For patients, healthcare facilities are not disjointed, and the perception of care carries across each department.

One positive CPC-28 screening cited sexual trauma history as a barrier to CCS completion. Trauma can not only cause an aversion to pelvic exams but may also lead to distrust of medical providers (Mkuu et al., 2022). Nearly 60% of veteran women report at least one instance of lifetime sexual violence while the rate for the general population of women in the U.S. sits as 36% (Danan et al., 2022). While sexual assault was not found to substantially decrease CCS participation in women veterans, sexual violence history does carry a cervical cancer risk which is twofold higher than the general population due to factors such as exposures

to HPV, higher instances of smoking, and increased risky behavior such as unprotected sex (Danan et al., 2022).

The goal for survey completions was at least 100 responses based on the simple, randomized sample size of 453, confidence level of 95% and a 10% margin of error. Availability of this principal investigator initially precluded contacts to evenings and weekends. Patients voiced wariness in the validity of the call based on it being outside of business hours. Approximately 3-4 weeks into the intervention period, a pivot to calls during the week did improve veteran participation. Patients overall were more apt to consent to receive CCS education than the survey without offering further insight into the reluctance.

CCS Completions

Sixteen percent ($n = 6$) of patients who received education did accomplish screening within 8-weeks of the intervention. The baseline metric, VHA ePerformance metric ccs01_ec: Cervical Ca Screen, was 65.91% for the facility in March 2023, which was below the Healthy People 2030 CCS goal of 84.3% (Popalis et al., 2022). This monthly performance indicator measured the percent screenings completed within the USPSTF guidelines; this project followed ccs01_ec as an outcome metric in assessing for intervention effectiveness (Appendix F).

Ten of the 37 educated patients who did not complete CCS were found to have been contacted during the intervention window by the mental health, primary care, and/or women's health departments for their respective services. However, post due CCS status was not brought up to alert the women during the encounter.

Seven of the 10 post intervention contacts were with mental health providers. A global meta-analysis found that women with mental health conditions were less likely to complete CCS, while in examining women in the U.S. the results showed mixed findings of a relationship

between mental health and CCS (Mkuu et al., 2023). For women in the U.S., substance use disorder (SUD) or the combination of SUD and mental health issues are associated with lower rates of CCS; the need exists for tailored CCS interventions in this population (Mkuu et al., 2023). Exploring the relationship between mental illness or SUD and CCS completion in veterans is out of the scope of this project. However, further study is warranted to identify the barriers to CCS among women veterans with mental health and/or SUD diagnoses. Nonetheless, systems issues within organizations resulting in disjointedness between primary care and mental health services contributed to lower CCS completion rates for patients with behavioral health conditions (Mkuu et al., 2022). A lack of communication between departments and behavioral health team disengagement in CCS leads to uncoordinated care (Mkuu et al., 2022).

Dissemination

Results and recommendations were shared with facility Women's' Health Leadership Performance Measures Committee, and the Primary Care and Women's health provider lunch and learn session. Patient narratives describing encounters which eroded trust were discussed; recommendations included collaboration with mental health clinical subject matter experts prior to implementation of any future CCS interventions and considerations for transgender patients.

Before and during the intervention window, the women's health department were also involved in efforts to ensure CCS procedures were correctly coded in the medical record, made active outreach to clinicians who deviated from the USPSTF CCS guidelines to include provider documentation of the deviation from standard so that the occurrence would not count against the CCS metric, ongoing efforts were also in place to increase women's health certified providers within the primary care team. During dissemination of findings to facility primary care providers, barriers mentioned by the group included difficulty in scheduling urgent appointments

for women's care due to the limited number of women health certified providers, patient preference for scarce female providers, and women health consults being returned incomplete. The primary care team also voiced concern of a lack of diagnostic follow-up for their patients after being seen by a certified women's health provider. It seemed as though the care was fractured, and it had yet to be determined which component of care each provider was responsible for. Providers certified in women's health maintain competency within the specialty, with the small number of women veterans it may be difficult for all providers to perform the number of procedures required to maintain credentialing and privileging. During the meeting, facility women's health coordinator added the continued issue of clinical reminders for CCS being ignored during encounters. There are some patients who visit a women's health provider for specific needs and remain under the care of their primary care provider. This strict delineation of roles was also mentioned by the providers as worrisome and a cause for delay in care for urgent examinations, it may also be contributing to the lower rates of CCS completion.

Limitations

Thirty-seven patients received CCS education, 12 of those patients also consented for the modified CPC-28 survey, four survey completions screened positive for barriers to CCS completion. It is of the human condition to recall negative encounters over positive; with this truth and small sample size, it is difficult to make recommendations based on narratives extracted from the survey participants or to conclude the observed increase in CCS metric as directly attributable to the intervention. Furthermore, this project sampled non-compliant patients, this may also have had an effect on survey responses as is the human condition to find fault outside of self when presented with non-compliant behavior. This project was also set in a

veteran's administration facility, as such, there are differences in patient demographics and federal directives guiding patient care which likely may not exist in non-VA hospitals.

Conclusion

The incidence of cervical cancer and resultant mortality rates associated with untimely detection remains a global public health priority (Arrivillaga et al., 2023). There are limited publications investigating methods to improve CCS rates within the veteran population; this quality improvement initiative sought to determine barriers to completion and share those with facility women's health leadership to support determining future, appropriate interventions. The logic model served as the framework for this project, which was useful during the intervention planning stages; the model was less valuable during the evaluation phase of the project. At the end of the intervention, the CCS eQM metric increased to 74.9%, which met the project goal of a 10% increase from a baseline of 64.9%. This project utilized the modified CPC-28 and found patient-reported barriers to timely CCS completion were lack of patient trust in the organization and gaps in patient knowledge regarding USPSTF guidelines for CCS completions. Facility providers also included barriers they observed with timely CCS completions including sequelae from a strict delineation of roles for women's health and primary care providers. Future endeavors for CCS interventions and service improvement would place stronger emphasis on aligned/coordinated care. Interventions may explore the patient and provider reported barriers with substantial input from mental/behavioral health professionals and include considerations for transgender individuals within the population.

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Appendix A

Figure 1: Logic Model Adaptation

Logic Model Adaptation

Program Action - Logic Model

Appendix B

Phone Call Protocol

Operator: Good evening, my name is [NAME]. I am calling from [the Women's Health Department at VA Long Beach]. Am I speaking with [WOMAN'S FULL NAME]?

Action: If yes, confirm patient identify using DOB or medical record number and the interview continues. If no, ask to speak with her. If it is the wrong number, politely end the phone call and hang up.

Operator: I am calling because you do not have an updated cervical cancer screening that is performed using the Papanicolaou test. This phone call is performed in the context of a quality improvement study and your participation is voluntary. Would it be possible to speak with you for one minute about the cervical cancer screening?

Action: If yes, the interview continues (Section 1 or 2, depending on if you are a clinician or MSA). If no, politely end the phone call and hang up.

*----- Skip to **Section 2** if you are a MSA, continue to **Section 1** if you are a clinician -----*

Section 1 – Continue from here if you are a clinician

Cervical Cancer Education Script :

Hi, I am [NAME] a [Physician/RN/NP/PA] with the Women's Health Department at VA Long Beach and I am here to tell you about a test that can save your life.

Did you know that Cervical Cancer is caused by a virus transmitted during intimate contact and is almost completely preventable with screening?

Any woman can get cervical cancer, and women who have early cervical cancer usually have no symptoms and feel perfectly healthy. So what's the best way to protect yourself? Get a pap test. Pap tests can find changes in cervical cells before they become cancer.

If you're over 30, in addition to your pap test, we recommend testing for high risk HPV types or Human Papillomavirus. This is because these HPV viruses are very common, and in most women go away without treatment. In some cases, however, the HPV virus does not go away and can cause changes in cells that over time can become cancer. Keep in mind that cervical cancer and pre-cancer is slow growing and takes many years to develop. If we catch it early, it can be completely cured through simple procedures done in the office, but we can only detect early cell changes if you get tested.

I know that getting a pap test can be a little embarrassing or maybe even a little uncomfortable, but our clinicians do everything we can to make this test as easy and comfortable as possible.

It's a simple procedure; after getting undressed, your doctor or nurse practitioner will use a speculum to take a look at your cervix. We use a brush on the surface of your cervix to take a sample of those cells. The whole test takes only about a minute. So who should get the pap test? All women between 21 and 65

should get a pap test every three to five years depending on guidance from your health care provider, even if you have had the HPV vaccine.

A pap test is important regardless of your sexual history or orientation. If you've had one sexual partner for many years or no sexual partners in the last few years or your partner's a woman, we still recommend getting tested because the HPV virus is so common. Remember, we can still do your pap test even when you are on your period.

So please, if you are between 21 and 65 get a pap test every three to five years depending on guidance from your health care provider. Do it for yourself. Do it for your family.

Cervical Cancer Screening Education Script :

Before we have you speak with our MSA to assist in scheduling a appointment, we would also like to ask a few questions regarding the issues you may have encountered with scheduling cervical cancer screenings in the past, these questions are also in conjunction with a quality improvement study and your involvement would be voluntary. Would you like to continue to the 1-2 minute questionnaire?

Action: If no, transfer to MSA for CCS scheduling. If yes, conduct questionnaire then transfer to MSA for scheduling.

Section 2 – Continue from here if you are a MSA

MSA: Can I schedule an appointment at your primary care unit [NAME OF YOUR PRIMARY CARE UNIT], to perform a Papanicolaou test, to update your cervical cancer screening status?

Action: If yes, the appointment is scheduled and the phone call is ended. Give additional information about the location of the primary care unit if this is needed. If no, politely end the phone call and hang up.

END

Appendix C

CPC-28 Questionnaire

(Beliefs about Papanicolaou and Cervical Cancer)

A. The following sentences are some ideas related to the Papanicolaou test (PAP) and cervical cancer (uterine cervix cancer). Please indicate with a cross the alternative that best describes your belief about each one of the sentences. There are no good or bad answers in this questionnaire, therefore if you are unsure or do not know an answer, feel free to answer what you believe.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1. Getting a Pap test makes me feel good because it means that I take care of my health.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. I do not have time to get a Pap test.*	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3. I have not taken the Pap test because they treat me badly in the health care center.*	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4. I do not know at what age it is necessary to have a Pap test.*	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
5. I have not taken a Pap test because when I go, I need to wait a long time to be seen.*	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6. The Pap can save my life.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
7. I have not taken the Pap test because I am afraid to find out if I have cancer.*	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
8. I have not taken the Pap test because the health care center is only open during hours when I cannot go.*	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
9. I have not taken the Pap test because I am embarrassed to have a genital exam.*	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
10. I do not know how often I need to get a Pap test.*	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
11. I have not taken a Pap test because it is difficult to get an appointment.*	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
12. Cervical cancer may lead to death.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
13. Cervical cancer may lead to a woman having a hysterectomy.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
14. Cervical cancer is a serious health problem.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
15. Cervical cancer can lead to a woman needing to receive chemotherapy or radiotherapy treatment.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

*Nine questions pertaining to patient barriers were included in this project

B. The following sentences are related to **the need that you have to take the Pap test, and the risk of having Cervical Cancer**. Please indicate the degree to which you agree or disagree with each statement. Remember, there are no good or bad answers in this questionnaire, therefore if you are unsure or do not know an answer, feel free to answer what you believe.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1. If I do not have symptoms, I do not need a Pap test.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. If I have not had children, I do not need a Pap test.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3. If I do not have intercourse, I do not need a Pap test.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4. I am at risk for developing cervical cancer.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
5. If I have cervical cancer, I can die.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6. Cervical cancer is one of the most common cancers among women my age.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

C. The following sentences are some reasons women have for getting a Pap test. Please indicate the degree of agreement in each sentence, thinking about **the reasons that have made you or would make you get a PAP test**. Remember, there are no good or bad answers in this questionnaire, therefore if you are unsure or do not know an answer, feel free to answer what you believe.

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1. To take care of my health.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
2. Because a nurse or midwife told me.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
3. Because a doctor told me.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
4. Because my mother spoke to me about it.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
5. Because a friend or neighbour spoke to me about it.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
6. Because members of my family told me to get it.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
7. Because I listened to or read something in the newspaper or in a television or radio program.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Appendix D

Author's Permission: Modified CPC-28 Tool

Inicio del mensaje reenviado:

De: "Harris, Dana" <dcharris2007@csu.fullerton.edu>

Fecha: 13 de agosto de 2023, 00:50:40 CLT

Para: Maria Teresa Urrutia <murrutis@uc.cl>

Asunto: Request for Permission: CPC-28

Dr. Urrutia,

I am a doctorate of nursing practice student at California State University, Fullerton in the United States. My nursing quality improvement project for the program concerns capturing patients' perceived barriers to completing timely Pap screenings. I would like to request to use the questions pertaining to barriers under section A of the tool in my project. I would contact patients of my facility's women's health department who are overdue for their screening and provide an educational script on the importance of completing timely screenings and I would deliver the CPC-28 questions #2-5 & 7-11 as well. This project has been exempted by the facility's institutional review board and we are preparing for the university review board later this month. The window to implement this project is anticipated for September through December 2023 and I plan to contact 100 patients to offer the education and apply the tool. Thank you very much for your time, I will await response.

Warmest Regards,

Dana C. Harris MSN, RN, CNOR

ph. +1 949.295.4268

dcharris2007@csu.fullerton.edu

From: Maria Teresa Urrutia Soto <maria.urrutia@unab.cl>
Subject: [External] RE: Request for Permission: CPC-28
Date: August 14, 2023 at 7:05:56 AM PDT
To: Maria Teresa Urrutia <murrutis@uc.cl>
Cc: "dcharris2007@csu.fullerton.edu" <dcharris2007@csu.fullerton.edu>, Maria Teresa Urrutia Soto <maria.urrutia@unab.cl>

External Email Use Caution and Confirm Sender

Of course that you can use it
Regards

Saludos,

Ma. Teresa Urrutia
PhD, MN, EM
Profesora Investigadora

República 217, piso 3. Santiago de CHILE.
Teléfono: (56-2) 2661-8922 Correo electrónico: maria.urrutia@unab.cl.
<https://investigacion.unab.cl/doctorados/doctorado-ciencia-enfermeria/>

“Tiene mucho más sentido ajustar nuestras necesidades a un planeta finito, que pretender ajustar el planeta a nuestras infinitas necesidades (Orr, 1991)”. Evite imprimir este correo.

AVISO DE CONFIDENCIALIDAD: Si usted recibió este mensaje por error, agradezco me informe y proceda a borrar el mensaje y los archivos adjuntos.

Appendix E

California State University Los Angeles IRB Exemption Letter

From: Riner, Claire <cbakewe@calstatela.edu>
Sent: Tuesday, September 26, 2023 12:42 PM
To: Yang, Kay <kyang49@calstatela.edu>
Cc: Winokur, Elizabeth <ewinoku2@exchange.calstatela.edu>; IRB <irb@calstatela.edu>; irb3 <irb3@calstatela.edu>
Subject: RE: DNP Project (SF23-6)

Good afternoon, Dr. Yang,

Thank you for submitting the "Is My Project Human Subjects Research" screening form. Based on the information submitted in this screening form and the description provided, this project ("Direct Clinician Contact to Improve Cervical Cancer Screening Participation in Veterans") does not seem to meet the definition of human subjects' research according to federal regulations (45 CFR 46), and therefore, does not require IRB review at this time. Please let me know if you have any further questions.

I cc'd two IRB-specific email addresses so that there is record of this correspondence there.

Best Regards,
Claire Riner

Claire Riner, M.P.A., CIP, ECoP
Research Support Services
Coordinator
Office of Research, Scholarship, and
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California State University, Los
Angeles
5151 State University Drive
Los Angeles, CA 90032
T 323.343.3792
E cbakewe@calstatela.edu

Appendix F

VHA Institutional Approval Letter

Institutional Approval Letter

May 10th, 2023

This letter is to show that, [redacted] as the Women Veterans Program Manager at VA [redacted] Healthcare System, give permission to Dana C. Harris to conduct the quality improvement project titled *Direct Clinician Contact to Improve Cervical Cancer Screening Participation in Veterans* on the following unit(s) Women’s Health Clinic and Primary Care Clinics with Women’s Health credentialed providers.

Upon obtaining all necessary clearances from the Nursing Research Committee, (and/or other entities in the facility as needed) at VA [redacted] Healthcare System, and after obtaining the necessary IRB determination/approval, the above-named project lead is allowed to:

- (1) access necessary documents/data
- (2) collect data including patient demographics and diagnostic results
- (3) access necessary documents/data
- (4) conduct necessary interactions with staff/patients relevant to their project

The project lead is responsible for ensuring that all activities related to conducting the project are in compliance with the policies that govern practice, HIPAA, and research-related regulations at VA [redacted] Healthcare System and its covered entities.

If you have any questions or concerns, please do not hesitate to contact me.

Signature: [redacted]
Digitally signed by [redacted] on 2023.05.10 2:27:04 -0700

Name: [redacted]

Title: Women Veterans Program Mgr.

Contact Information: [redacted]

Signature:

Name:

Title:

Contact Information:

Appendix G

Table 1: Facility ePerformance Metric ccs01_ec: Cervical Cancer Screen

Table 1.

ePerformance Metric ccs01_ec

%CCS Completions	Timeframe
65.91%	FY23Q2 Baseline
66.9%	FY23Q3
68.6%	FY23Q4
74.9%	FY24Q1 Intervention
74.9%	FY24 YTD*

Note. Data updated as of 1/10/2024.

Patient	Outcome								
	A2	A3 ¹	A4	A5	A7	A8	A9	A10 ²	A11
	I don't have time to get a pap test	I have not taken the pap test because they treat me badly in the healthcare center	I do not know at which age it is necessary to have a pap test	I have not taken a pap test because when I go, I need to wait a long time to be seen	I have not taken the pap test because I am afraid to find out if I have cancer	I have not taken the pap test because the healthcare center is only open during hours when I cannot go	I have not taken the pap test because I am embarrassed to have a genital examination	I do not know how often I need to get a pap test	I have not taken a pap test because it is difficult to get an appointment
P6	D	D	A	D	D	D	D	A	D
P7	D	D	D	D	D	D	D	D	D
P8	D	D	D	D	D	D	D	D	D
P9	D	A	D	D	D	D	D	D	D
P10	D	D	D	D	D	D	D	D	D
P11	A	SD	D	D	D	D	D	D	D
P12	D	A	D	D	D	D	D	D	D

SA= Strongly Agree A=Agree D= Disagree SD= Strongly Disagree

Note. Highlighted answers indicate positive screen for barriers. ¹Primary reported barrier. ²Secondary reported barrier.

Appendix I

Table 3: CPC-28 Patient Narrative Responses

Table 3.

Patient Narratives Captured During CPC-28 Questionnaire

Survey Narratives

I would only like to have my PAP through my HMO, not through VA

It is difficult to know when the screening is due

Nurse gatekeeps access to my provider

I had to go to urgent care for my UTI because my care team did not follow up on my labs, if I can't trust them with a UTI then I definitely don't trust them w/ my cervical cancer screening

I was told I was overdue for my pap and causing their numbers to be bad

This is the first time someone has contacted me regarding cervical cancer screening

I have sexual trauma history

Survey Narratives

My care team was not friendly, I think they may be experiencing compassion fatigue

I am in pain from a nerve d/o and the VA is denying my claims for care, I am approved for women's health care but my other claims are being denied.

I had a VA physician not take my blood pressure seriously, I sought care at a private organization and will have my PAP done there.
